

Antibacterial Activity of Organic Extracts of Root Bark of *Ziziphus jujube* Gaertn(L) var. *hysudrica* Edgew

Dure-E-Shahwar^{1*}, Khalid Hussain¹, Nadeem Irfan Bukhari¹, Zafar Iqbal², Amna Shoaib³, Naureen Shahzadi¹, Freeha Rafique¹

¹University College of Pharmacy, University of the Punjab, Allama Iqbal Campus, 54000 Lahore, Pakistan

²Applied Chemistry Research Centre, PCSIR Laboratories Complex, 54000 Lahore, Pakistan

³Institute of Agricultural Science, University of the Punjab, Quaid-e-Azam Campus, 54000 Lahore, Pakistan

Key words: Root bark, Extraction, UV-Visible spectroscopy, IR spectroscopy, Antibacterial Activity.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.12692/ijb/16.1.251-260>

Article published on January 15, 2020

Abstract

Extracts of root bark of *Ziziphus jujube* Gaertn(L) var. *hysudrica* Edgew were prepared by using organic solvents having different polarity i.e methanol, acetone, ethyl acetate, dichloromethane, chloroform and n-hexane. Extracts were then subjected to various characterization studies including UV-Visible and IR profiling. UV-Visible spectrum has shown multiple peaks for all the extracts in UV region. Dichloromethane and chloroform extracts have shown similar pattern as compared to the other extracts. IR spectrum has shown strong –OH (3336.0 cm^{-1}) band for methanol and acetone extracts whereas ethylacetate, dichloromethane, chloroform and n-hexane extracts have shown distinct C-N ($1250\text{-}1020\text{ cm}^{-1}$) stretch band for amines. All the extracts except n-hexane as it was less in yield were screened for antibacterial potential against two gram negative strains (*Escherchia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) and two gram positive strains (*Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus pumilus*) by using disc diffusion assay. Maximum activity was shown by ethylacetate extract against *Eescherchia coli* and *Bacillus pumilus* having zone of inhibition 13.66 mm and 12 mm respectively. Dichloromethane extract has shown high activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* having zone of inhibition 10.66 mm. chloroform extract was high in term of antibacterial activity against *Bacillus subtilis* having zone of inhibition 12 mm. data was statistically analyzed by using one-way ANOVA p value less than 0.05 was considered significant. Multiple comparisons were performed by using LSD test.

*Corresponding Author: Dure-E-Shahwar ✉ dr_dure2010@hotmail.com

Introduction

Zizyphus Jujuba (L.) Gaertn. Var. *hysudrica* Edgew is a hybrid of two *Zizyphus* species namely *Zizyphus mauritiana* and *Zizyphus spina-christi* (Azam-Ali *et al.*, 2006). It grows as medium sized tree possessing leaves which appear glabrous on both surfaces. The plant is rarely seen in wild-form and is usually cultivated to obtain its fruit which is edible. The fruit usually attains maximum of 1-inch length in wild-form in contrast to its cultivated form where it may reach up to the length of 3-inch long and is almost half as wide as its length (Chaudhry, 1969). This variety is distributed in punjab region of Pakistan. *Z. mauritiana* occurs in form of small shrubs to medium sized tree. The natural habitat of plant is warm subtropics and tropics of South Asia where it exist in its wild form. The cultivated form of plant spreads through Indo-China and Southren China East ward whereas through Malesia it spreads to South East ward. In contrast *Z. spina-christi* belongs to drier tropical areas of Middle East, Ethiopia, North-East Africa and Eastren Africa. In Iran, Saudi Arabia and farther west Turkey it exist in its wild fom. In India, Pakistan, Egypt, Syria, the Mahgreb, Saharan Oases and Zanzibar it exists as minor cultivated plant. (Azam-Ali *et al.*, 2006)

The species of *Zizyphus* are enriched in phytochemicals including various Vitamins like vitamin-C (Bakhshi and singh, 1974; Singh *et al.*, 1973), vitamin-B₁ (Thiamine), vitamin-B₂ (Riboflavin) (Trojan and Kruglyakov, 1972 ; Kuliev and Guseinova, 1974), Alkaloids, (Pareek, 2001; Tschesche *et al.*, 1976; Tschesche *et al.*, 1979; Han *et al.*, 1990 ; Jossang *et al.*, 1996), Carbohydrates (Bakhshi and singh, 1974; Singh *et al.*, 1973) and heteropolysacchrides like Pectin-A (Tomoda *et al.*, 1985), Glycosides like Flavonoid Glycosides/ Spinosins (Woo *et al.*, 1979), various acids like Triterpenoic Acids (Lee *et al.*, 2003) , Betulinic Acid (Pisha *et al.*, 1995; Kim *et al.*, 1998 ; Eizhamer and Xu, 2004), Oleanolic acid (Hsu *et al.*, 1997), Saponins like Glycoside saponin (Ogihara *et al.*, 1976), Phospholipids (Goncharova *et al.*, 1990), Inorganic minerals like Calcium and phosphorous (Bakhshi and

singh, 1974; Singh *et al.*, 1973), metal ions like iron (Bakhshi and singh, 1974; Singh *et al.*, 1973), proteins and carotenes (Bakhshi and singh, 1974; Singh *et al.*, 1973).

Infectious diseases remain one of the major disasters responsible for morbidity and mortality among human beings and animals. The main factors which drive attention towards natural antimicrobials includes undesirable effects of synthetic antimicrobials, emergence of multi drug resistance and limited antimicrobial spectrum (Ngoci *et al.*, 2014). Since prehistoric time different parts of medicinal plants were used traditionally to cure specific ailments. Pharmacological potential of medicinal plants is associated with presence of different bioactive compounds like alkaloids, phenolics, flavonoids, glycosides, tannins, essential oil, steroids, terpenoids and others. Folklore medicine provide base to develop current drugs available today depending upon information about curative agents in them. Between 1983-1994 78% of new drugs were obtained from natural source and were used unmodified or in partly synthetic form according to United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) (Sharmin *et al.*, 2014; Ngoci *et al.*, 2014). Bioactive metabolites vary in amount from plant to plant and in different parts of the same plant. Extraction of these metabolites depends upon two main factors i.e nature of extracting solvent and method adopted for extraction. In this study the extraction of bioactive metabolites was carried out by using six different solvents having different polarities i.e methanol, acetone, ethyl acetate, dichloromethane, chloroform and n-hexane. These extracts were analysed by UV-Vis spectrophotometer and FT-IR. The antimicrobial activity of all extracts was monitored against two gram negative bacteria i.e. *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas* and two gram positive bacteria i.e. *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus pumilus* by using disc diffusion assay.

Materials and method

Collection of plant material

Zizyphus jujube Gaertn (L) variety *hysudrica* Edgew

was collected from Lahore, Pakistan. The bark of the root was separated from the inner root by physical means. Which was then shade dried for 10 days and ground, sieved and got properly stored in desiccator.

Chemicals

All the material and reagents used to conduct this study were taken from PCSIR Labs complex and University of the Punjab Lahore. All the chemicals were of AR grade and used as such without further purification.

Preparation of extracts

Hundred grams of each finely ground root bark and root of *ZizyphusJujuba* (L.) Gaertn. Var. *hysudrica*Edgew was poured into six different flasks and extracted against various solvent having different polarities like: methanol, acetone, ethyl acetate, dichloromethane,*n*-hexane and chloroform. Flasks were allowed to continuously stir for 72 hours the material was then filtered and the resulting filtrates were air dried.

Characterization studies

Characterization of root bark extracts in different solvents was done by using UV-Visible and IR spectrum studies.

U.V-Visible Spectrum

The solution of all dried extracts in respective solvents were made and got scanned at 200-800nm to determine λ_{max} (Asif *et. al.*, 2014).

IR Spectrum

The dried extracts in different solvents were converted into disc and got scanned at mid IR region (650-4000 cm^{-1}) to find the functional groups involved in various vibrations (Asif *et. al.*,2014).

Estimation of antibacterial potential

Test Bacteria

Antibacterial activity was performed by using two Gram positive strains i-e *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus pumilus* and two Gram negative strains i-e *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonasaeruginosa*. These

strains were obtained from microbiology laboratory of University College of pharmacy, university of the Punjab, Lahore. After getting above mentioned strains standard confirmatory tests were performed with them.

Bacterial Culture and Preparation of Media

Nutrient agar media was used to perform in-vitro antibacterial activity. Sterilized water suspensions of six isolated and pure strains of bacteria (*Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.) were prepared and got mixed with nutrient agar separately for evaluation of antibacterial activity. Media temperature was maintained at 45°C which was then poured into petri dishes and allowed to solidify.

Antibacterial activity using Disc Diffusion Method

Disc diffusion method was used for studying antibacterial activity as described by Sharma *etal.*, 2013. Fresh culture suspension of gram positive and gram negative bacteria was spread uniformly on media containing petri dishes. Filter paper disc having 6mm diameter soaked with extract (1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) was placed on the surface of media agar plates. Plates were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours under optimum conditions.

Results and discussion

The overlay of UV-Visible scan of different extracts of bark of roots was given in Figure 1.

These results showed that the spectra of DCM and chloroform extracts were entirely distinct from the other extracts. All other extracts showed somewhat similar pattern, however, peaks intensities were different which may be due to the difference in concentration of compounds. This is due to the presence of similar compound or compounds having similar UV-Visible absorbance pattern. It is interesting that all the extracts absorbed in UV region indicating the presence of compounds having unsaturated structure and chromophores. For all the extracts multiple peaks were obtained instead of single peak.

Fig. 1. UV-VISIBLE scans of different extracts of root bark of *Ziziphus jujube* Gaertn(L) var. *hysudrica* Edgew.

Presence of conjugated pi-bonding system having $\pi - \pi^*$ transition was indicated by the absorbance bands between wavelength range of 200-280nm. As larger the conjugated pi-system became there will be corresponding narrowing of energy gap for $\pi - \pi^*$ transition and longer the wavelength of light

absorbed have occurred. Second transition which was between non-bonding (lone pair) electrons to a π^* anti-bonding M.O was observed by the presence of absorbance bands in the wavelength range of 300-370nm and was referred to as n- π^* transition.

Fig. 2. IR spectrum of different extracts of root bark of *Ziziphus jujube* Gaertn (L) var. *hysudrica* Edgew.

The highest bonding p-orbital are lower in terms of energy as compared to non-bonding (n) M.Os. So, the energy gap for $\pi - \pi^*$ were higher than n- π^* transitions that's why n- π^* peak was attained at longer wavelength. In general $\pi - \pi^*$ transitions are

stronger than n- π^* transitions which are weaker in terms of less light is absorbed to carry out n- π^* transition (Armando *et. al.*, 2013). ATR-IR spectra of different extracts of root bark of *Ziziphus jujube* Gaertn (L) Var. *hysudrica* Edgew were given in

Figure 2. These results showed that the functional groups of acetone and methanol extracts were alike but different from other extracts. Both the extracts showed strong band of OH (3336.0 cm^{-1}), C=O (1654.0 cm^{-1}), N-O (1094.0 cm^{-1}) and N-H (1604.6 cm^{-1}). Whereas, DCM, n-hexane, chloroform and ethyl acetate extracts showed similar profile

indicating functional groups such as C-H Stretch ($3000-2800\text{ cm}^{-1}$), C-H bending ($1000-700\text{ cm}^{-1}$), C=O ($1750-1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$), C-O ($1250-1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$), C-F ($2000-1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$), C=C ($1660-1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and C-N ($1250-1020\text{ cm}^{-1}$). Moreover, $\alpha\beta$ unsaturated band (1684.8 cm^{-1}) was only shown in DCM extract.

Fig. 3. Antibacterial activity of different extracts of root bark of *Ziziphus jujube* Gaertn(L) var. *hysudrica* Edgew against *Escherichia coli*.

Results of antibacterial activity of root bark of *Ziziphus jujube* Gaertn(L) var. *hysudrica* Edgew against *Escherichia coli* were given in figure 3. Ethylacetate, dichloromethane and chloroform extracts differ significantly from each other in term of antibacterial activity.

Highest activity was shown by ethylacetate extract having zone of inhibition 13.66 mm. whereas for other extracts i-e acetone, methanol, dichloromethane and chloroform the zone of inhibition was 8.66 mm, 8.33 mm, 5.66 mm and 5 mm respectively.

Results of antibacterial activity of root bark of *Ziziphus jujube* Gaertn(L) var. *hysudrica* Edgew against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were given in figure 4. Extracts do not differ from each other in

term of antibacterial activity ($p < 0.05$). Highest activity was shown by dichloromethane extract having zone of inhibition 10.66 mm. whereas for other extracts i-e ethylacetate, methanol, chloroform and acetone the zone of inhibition was 9 mm, 9 mm, 8 mm and 5 mm respectively.

Results of antibacterial activity of root bark of *Ziziphus jujube* Gaertn(L) var. *hysudrica* Edgew against *Bacillus pumilus* were given in figure 5.

Extracts do not differ from each other in term of antibacterial activity ($p < 0.05$). Highest activity was shown by ethylacetate extract having zone of inhibition 12 mm. whereas for other extracts i-e acetone, chloroform, methanol and dichloromethane the zone of inhibition was 10.33 mm, 9.33 mm, 6 mm and 5 mm respectively.

Fig. 4. Antibacterial activity of different extracts of root bark of *Ziziphus jujube* Gaertn(L) var. *hysudrica* Edgew against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Results of antibacterial activity of root bark of *Ziziphus jujube* Gaertn (L) var. *hysudrica* Edgew against *Bacillus subtilis* were given in figure 6. The extracts do not differ from each other in term of antibacterial activity ($p < 0.05$). Highest activity was

shown by chloroform extract having zone of inhibition 12 mm. whereas for other extracts i-e ethylacetate, acetone, dichloromethane and methanol the zone of inhibition was 11.66 mm, 11.33 mm, 10.66 mm and 10 mm respectively.

Fig. 5. Antibacterial activity of different extracts of root bark of *Ziziphus jujube* Gaertn(L) var. *hysudrica* Edgew against *Bacillus pumilus*.

In present study it was clearly seen that antibacterial activity was shown by all extracts in different organic solvents. Mostly in plants antimicrobial activity was

attributed to alkaloids and flavonoids both of which are secondary metabolites (Compean and Ynaluz, 2014). The solvents having high polarity may extract

phenolics and flavonoids better that's why activity shown by these extracts i-e methanol and acetone and was attributed to phenolics and flavonoids present in respective extract. Whereas solvents having low

polarity may extract alkaloids better that's why activity shown by these extracts i-e ethylacetate dichloromethane and chloroform was attributed to alkaloids present in respective extracts.

Fig. 6. Antibacterial activity of different extracts of root bark of *Ziziphus jujube* Gaertn(L) var. *hysudrica* Edgew against *Bacillus subtilis*

These statements were also strongly supported by IR spectrum of various extracts given in figure 2. It was evident from IR spectrum that very distinct peak for –OH (3336.0 cm^{-1}) group was present in both methanol and acetone extracts. Whereas ethylacetate, dichloromethane and chloroform a distinct peak for –C-N ($1250\text{-}1020\text{ cm}^{-1}$) group was observed which was an amine stretch peak confirms the presence of alkaloids in these extracts.

Genus *Ziziphus* comprised up of 40 different species distributed in subtropical and warm temperate zones. *Ziziphus* has been used since past many years as a traditional medicine for the treatment of various diseases like anemia, diabetes, fever, liver complaints, urinary infections, skin infections, liver complains, digestive disorders, bronchitis, diarrhea and others (Mishra and Bhatia., 2014 ; Goyal *et. al.*, 2012). Plants belonging to genus *Ziziphus* have demonstrated high potential to develop natural antibiotics as indicated in literature (Emad *et. al.*, 2017 ; Mirza *et. al.*, 2016 ; Mishra and Bhatia., 2014 ; Hossain *et. al.*, 2013 ;

Dhunmati *et. al.*, 2013 ; Dangogoo *et. al.*, 2012 ; Ahmad *et. al.*, 2011 ; Abalaka *et. al.*, 2010).

It was also evaluated that bioactive components responsible for antibacterial activity were phenolics and alkaloids present in plant extracts (Rizwan *et. al.*, 2017; Bukar *et. al.*, 2015; Compean and Ynaluz, 2014; Mehbuba *et. al.*, 2010). The possible mechanisms of action through which extracts have shown antibacterial effect includes interference with the formation of extracellular polysaccharides resulting in disruption of cell morphology (Hasnah *et. al.*, 2019; Yenugu *et. al.*, 2006), disruption of membrane integrity resulting in electrolyte leakage from cell (Walsh *et. al.*, 2003) inhibition of bacterial enzyme activity and interference with microbial DNA functioning resulting in cell death (Omojate *et. al.*, 2014).

Conclusion

Extraction of root bark of *Ziziphus jujube* Gaertn(L) var. *hysudrica* Edgew was done by using six different

organic solvents of varying polarities (methanol, acetone, ethyl acetate, dichloromethane, chloroform and n-hexane). Characterization was done by using UV-Visible and IR profiles of extracts in order to understand how the nature of unsaturation and different functional groups will be affecting the activity of extracts. Antibacterial potential of all the extracts except n-hexane (as its yield was very low) was estimated by using disc diffusion method against two gram negative strains (*Escherchia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) and two gram positive strains (*Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus pumilus*) bacterial strains. Maximum activity was shown by ethylacetate extract against *Escherchia coli* and *Bacillus pumilus* having zone of inhibition 13.66 mm and 12 mm respectively. Dichloromethane extract has shown high activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* having zone of inhibition 10.66 mm. chloroform extract was high in term of antibacterial activity against *Bacillus subtilis* having zone of inhibition 12 mm. Antibacterial activity was shown by all the extracts to different extent and was attributed to C-N band (1250-1020 cm^{-1}) in IR spectrum for alkaloids in ethylacetate, dichloromethane and chloroform extracts and OH band (3336.0 cm^{-1}) in IR spectrum for phenolics / flavonoids in methanol and acetone extracts.

References

- Abalaka ME, Daniyan SY, Mann A.** 2010. Evaluation of the antimicrobial activities of two *Ziziphusspecies* (*Ziziphusmauritiana* L. and *Ziziphus spina-christi* L.) on some microbial pathogens. African Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology **4**, 135-139.
- Ahmad B, Khan I, Bashir S, Azam S, Hussain F.** 2011. Screening of *Zizyphusjujuba* for antibacterial, phytotoxic and haemagglutination activities. African Journal of Biotechnology **10**, 2514-2519.
- Armando G, Francisco A, Mepivoseth C, Victorino M, Ismael L, José CZ, Córdova A.** 2013. Determination of the Biodiesel Content in Petrodiesel/Biodiesel Blends: A Method Based on Uv-Visible Spectroscopy and Chemometrics Tools. American Journal of Analytical Chemistry **4**, 273-276.
- Asif M, Hussain K, Bukhari NI, Khan MT, Latif A, Shahwar D, Shehzadi N, Shahbaz H, Khan HH.** 2014. Effect of pH on adsorption profile of *Phoenix sylvestris* pits activated carbon using paracetamol as a model drug. Latin American Journal of Pharmacy **33**, 1561-1566.
- Azam-Ali S, Bonkougou E, Bowe C, deKock C, Godara A, Williams JT.** 2006. Ber and OtherJujubes. International centre for underutilized crops, Southampton,UK.
- Bakhshi JC, Singh P.** 1974. The ber - a good choice for semi-arid and marginal soils. Indian Horticulture **19**, 27-30.
- Bukar AM, Kyari MZ, Gwaski PA, Guduso M, Kuburi FS, Abadam YI.** 2015. Evaluation of phytochemical and potential antibacterial activity of *Ziziphus spina-christi* L. against some important pathogenic bacteria obtained from university of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital, Maiduguri Borno state – Nigeria. Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry **3**, 98-101.
- Chaudhry SA.** 1969. Flora in Lyallpur & the Adjacent canal colony Districts. West Pakistan Agricultural University Layallpur, Pakistan.
- Compean KL, Ynaluz AR.** 2014. Antimicrobial activity of plant secondary metabolites: A Review. Journal of Medicinal Plants **8**, 204-2013.
- Eiznhamer D, Xu Z.** 2004. Betulinic acid: a promising anticancer candidate. IDrugs:The investigational drugs journal **4**, 359-373.
- Emad MA.** 2017. Antibacterial activity of fruit methanol extract of *Ziziphus spina-christi* from Sudan. International Journal of Current Microbiology

and Applied Sciences **6**, 38-44.

Goyal M, Nagori BP, Sasmal D. 2012. Review on ethnomedicinal uses, pharmacological activity and phytochemical constituents of *Ziziphus mauritiana* (*Z. jujuba* Lam., non-Mill). *Spatula DD* **2**, 107-116.

Goncharova NP, Isamukhamedov ASH, Glushenkova AI. 1990. Lipids of *Ziziphus jujuba*. *Chemistry of Natural Compounds* **26**, 16-18.

Han BH, Park MH, Han YN. 1990. Cyclic peptide and peptide alkaloids from seeds of *Ziziphus vulgaris*. *Phytochemistry* **29**, 3315- 3319.

Hasnah BSGK, Zohairah S, Nurul IMS, Azlin SRR. 2019. Antibacterial activity of methanol extracts of *Ziziphus mauritiana* leaves on carcinogenic bacteria. *E-Academia Journal*, 177-187.

Hossain MS, Uddin N, Hasan N, Hossain MP, Mondal M, Islam T, Faruque A, Rana MS. 2013. Phytochemical, cytotoxic, in-vitro antioxidant and anti-microbial investigation of ethanolic leaf extract of *Ziziphus rugosa* Lam. *Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences* **6**, 74-81.

Hsu HY, Yang JJ, Lin CC. 1997. Effects of oleanolic acid and ursolic acid on inhibiting tumour growth and enhancing the recovery of hematopoietic system postirradiation in mice. *Cancer Letters* **111**, 7-13.

Jossang A, Zahir A, Diakite D. 1996. Mauritian J, a cyclopeptide alkaloid from *Ziziphus mauritiana*. *Phytochemistry* **42**, 565-567.

Kim DSHL, Pezzuto JM, Pisha E. 1998. Synthesis of betulonic acid derivatives with activity against human melanoma. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters* **8**, 1707-1712.

Kuliev AA, Guseinova NK. 1974. The content of vitamin C, B₁, B₂ and E in some fruits. *Referativnyi Zhurnal* **2**, 69-73.

Lee S, Min B, Lee C, Kim K, Kho Y. 2003. Cytotoxic triterpenoids from the fruits of *Ziziphus jujuba*. *Planta Medica* **69**, 1051-1054.

Mehbuba BN, Rabia OA, Nabil AS, Asma YA. 2010. Evaluation of antibacterial and antioxidant activities of *Artemisia campestris* (Astraceae) and *Ziziphus lotus* (Rhamnaceae). *Arabian Journal of Chemistry* **2**, 79-84.

Mishra T, Bhatia A. 2014. Antiplasmodial effects of the aqueous ethanolic seed extract of *Ziziphus mauritiana* against *Plasmodium berghei* in Swiss albino mice. *International Journal of Pharmacological Research* **4**, 111-116.

Ngoci NS, Ramadhan M, Ngari MS, Leonard OP. 2014. Screening for antimicrobial activity of *Cissampelos pareira* L. methanol root extract. *European Journal of Medicinal Plants* **4**, 45-51.

Ogihara Y, Inoue O, Otsuka H, Kawai KI, Tanimura T, Shibata S. 1976. Droplet counter current chromatography for the separation of plant products. *Journal of Chromatography* **128**, 218-223.

Omojate GC, Enwa FO, Jewo AO, Eze CO. 2014. Mechanisms of antimicrobial actions of phytochemicals against enteric pathogens- A Review. *Journal of Pharmaceutical, Chemical and Biological Sciences* **2**, 77-85.

Pareek OP. 2001. *Fruits for the Future 2: Ber.* International Centre for Underutilised Crops, University of Southampton, Southampton, UK.

Pisha E, Chai H, Lee I, Chagwedera T, Farnsworth N, Cordell G, Beecher C, Fong H, Kinghorn A, Brown D. 1995. Discovery of betulonic acid as a selective inhibitor of human melanoma that functions by induction of apoptosis. *Nature Medicine* **10**, 1046-1051.

Rizwan A, Niyaz A, Atta AN. 2017. *Ziziphusoxyphylla*: Ethnobotanical,

Ethnopharmacological and Phytochemical review. *Biomedicine and Pharmacotherapy* **91**, 970-998.

Sharma V, Agrawal RC, Pandey S. 2013. Phytochemical screening and determination of antibacterial and antioxidant potential of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* root extracts. *Journal of Environmental Research and Development* **7**, 1552-1558.

Sharmin T, Chowdhury SR, Mian MY, Hoque M, Sumsujjaman M, Nahar F. 2014. Evaluation of antimicrobial activities of some Bangladeshi medicinal plants. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* **2**, 170-175.

Singh JP, Singh IS. 1973. Some promising varieties of ber. *Indian Horticulture* **18**, 3-4.

Tomoda M, Shimuju N, Gonda R. 1985. Pectic substances. II. The location of O-acetyl groups and the Smith degradation of *Ziziphus* Pectin A. *Chemical and Pharmaceutical Bulletin* **33**, 4017-4020.

Troyan AV, Kruglyakov GN. 1972. Produce with high vitamin content. *Sadovodstvo* **12**, 30.

Tschesche R, Khokhar I, Wilhelm H, Eckhardt G. 1976. Jubanin A and jubanin-B, new cyclopeptide

alkaloids from *Ziziphus jujuba*. *Phytochemistry* **15**, 541-542.

Tschesche R, Shah AH, Eckhardt G. 1979. Sativanine-A and sativanine-B, two new cyclopeptide alkaloids from the bark of *Ziziphus sativa*. *Phytochemistry* **18**, 702-704.

Walsh SE, Maillard JY, Russel AD, Catrenich CE, Charbonneau AL, Bartolo RG. 2003. Activity and mechanism of action of selected bacteriocidal agents on gram positive and gram negative bacteria. *Journal of Applied Microbiology* **94**, 240-247.

Woo WS, Kang SS, Shim SH, Wagner H, Chari VM, Seligmann O, Obermeier G. 1979. The structure of spinosin (2"-O-beta-glucosyliswertisin) from *Ziziphus vulgaris* var. *spinosa* (seeds). *Phytochemistry* **18**, 353-355.

Yenugu S, Hamil KG, French FS, Hall SH. 2006. Antimicrobial actions of human and macaque sperm associated antigen (SPAG) isoforms: influence of the N-terminal peptide. *Molecular and Cellular Biochemistry* **284**, 25-37.